

FLEXURAL FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF NEW ENGINEERED BIOCOMPOSITES FROM POLY (3-HYDROXYBUTYRATE-CO-HYDROXYVALERATE) (PHBV)/POLY (BUTYLENE ADIPATE-CO-TEREPHTHALATE) (PBAT) BLENDS AND SWITCHGRASS

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1 Introduction

Recently, environment friendly biodegradable composites made of biopolymer matrix reinforced with natural fibres have been developed in order to compete with conventional composites. Pre-blend of poly (3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV)/ poly (butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT) incorporated of switchgrass were successfully produced by injection molding as new biocomposites [1]. It was shown that the addition of compatilizer, poly diphenylmethane diisocyanate (pMDI) improved the tensile properties and heat deflection temperature of the compatibilized biocomposite compared to the virgin composites of PHBV/PBAT/switchgrass [1].

The mechanical damage caused by cyclic loads in fatigue loading results in a material failure at stress levels that are lower than the static strength. For this reason, in this study, flexural fatigue behavior of two switchgrass based biocomposites was investigated using the four point bending test. The matrix material of the composite systems was a pre-blend of poly (3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV)/ poly (butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT). PHBV-PBAT blend with (i) 30 wt% switchgrass; (ii) 30 wt% switchgrass and 0.75 parts by weight compatibilizer, poly diphenylmethane diisocyanate (pMDI), were selected for this investigation. Furthermore, the fracture surfaces of tested specimens were also examined since it has been shown that SEM micrograph observation could

be useful to study the failure mechanisms of composites under flexural fatigue loading [2].

2 Materials and methods

Switchgrass was obtained from Notts Farms in Clinton, Ontario, Canada whereas Pre-blend of 45% PHBV and 55% PBAT was procured from Tianan Biologic Materials Company Ltd., China. The compatibilizer pMDI was supplied by Huntsman Polyurethanes, Canada. Pre-blend pellets and switchgrass were dried prior to extrusion melt mixing followed by injection molding. Details of the biocomposite fabrication were described fully in the paper mentioned previously [1].

The flexural specimens were bars of rectangular cross section whose dimensions were 135mm × 12,7mm × 3,2mm. The flexural properties were measured according to ASTM standards D6272-02 (2008). The flexural fatigue tests were performed on a MTS servo hydraulic machine (Fig.1) using load control mode at R=0.1 ratio (Fig.2). The testing frequency was 5Hz. Test specimens of the biocomposites with and without compatibilizer were subjected to fatigue tests in four points bending under various loading levels of 80%, 70%, 60%, 50% and 40% of flexural static strength of the materials. At least five specimens were tested at each loading level.

Fig. 1. Flexural fatigue testing set-up,

Fig. 2. Load and displacement chart.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Fatigue life

Data on fatigue life of the two studied biocomposites are presented in Tables 1 and 2 whereas their S-N curves are illustrated in Fig.3. It can be seen that the

addition of the compatibilizer increases significantly both flexural static and fatigue strengths of the PHBV-PABT/switchgrass (30 wt%) biocomposite.

Table 1. Fatigue strength of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG biocomposite at R=0.1 and 5Hz.

Maximum alternative stress (MPa)		Number of cycles to failure
Static strength	37.42±0.86	1
80% Static strength	29.94±0	1057±165
70% Static strength	26.19±0	2266±663
60% Static strength	22.45±0	6471±880
50% Static strength	18.71±0	29561±2376
40% Static strength	14.97±0	172686±43438

Table 2. Fatigue strength of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG+0.75 phr pMDI biocomposite at R=0.1 and 5Hz.

Maximum alternative stress (MPa)		Number of cycles to failure
Static strength	46.79±1.15	1
80% Static strength	37.71±0.00	990±354
70% Static strength	33.00±0.00	2237±633
60% Static strength	28.28±0.00	8015±3188
50% Static strength	23.57±0.00	46113±16546
40% Static strength	18.86±0.00	329053±79615

Fig. 3. Fatigue life of two studied materials: PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG and PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG+0.75 phr pMDI biocomposites at R=0.1 and 5Hz.

3.2 Fractography

Fig. 4. Photographs of fractured specimens at final stage showing initial tensile cracks in tested specimens of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG composite under (a) flexural static loading, (b) fatigue loading at 40% of flexural static strength, $R=0.1$, 5Hz; and of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG + 0.75 phr pMDI composite under (c) flexural static loading, (d) fatigue loading at 40% of flexural static strength, $R=0.1$, 5Hz.

Fig. 5. Micrograph of fracture surfaces of a specimen of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG biocomposite under flexural static loading.

Fig. 6. Micrograph of the fracture surfaces of a specimen of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG + 0.75 phr pMDI biocomposite under flexural fatigue loading at 40% of flexural static strength, $R=0.1$, 5Hz.

Fig. 4. shows the photographs of broken specimens at the end of the tests for the studied materials under static and fatigue loadings. All specimens have

initial cracking at tensile loading side independently of the loading mode.

Figures 5 and 6 present the V shape fracture surfaces of specimens under flexural static and fatigue loadings which contain two failure zones. The first one represents tensile failure mode and the second seems to be caused by compression stress.

Fig. 7 shows SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of a specimen of biocomposite reinforced with switchgrass under flexural static loading. Details of the failure zones are presented in Fig.8. It can be seen that the tensile and compressive failure modes are well different. The first one is very rough having craters showing fibres and matrix pulled out whereas the second one, caused by abrasion, is much smoother. Furthermore, the compressive zone which looks smaller than the tensile failure one, suggests that the initial cracking might be caused by tension stress. The neutral axis zone had both failure modes. There is no transition line clearly observed.

Fig. 7. SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of a specimen of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG composite under flexural static loading.

Fig. 8. Details of the three different zones presented in fig. 7: (a) tensile failure, (b) middle, (c) compressive failure.

Poor fibre-matrix interface adhesion in the case of uncompatibilized biocomposite under flexural static loading is shown in figure 9.

Fig. 9. SEM micrographs of biocomposite with 30 wt% switchgrass under flexural static loading showing poor matrix-fibre interface adhesion.

The same pattern of failure surface as in the previous case can be observed in Fig. 10 and 11 for the compatibilized biocomposite reinforced with switchgrass. However, for the adhesion at interface, the quality is difference. Fig. 12 shows positive effect of the compatibilizer on the matrix-fibre interface adhesion.

Fig. 11. Details of the three different zones presented in fig. 10: (a) tensile failure, (b) middle, (c) compressive failure.

Fig. 10. SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of a specimen of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG + 0.75 phr pMDI composite under flexural static loading.

Fig. 12. SEM micrographs of biocomposite with 30 wt% switchgrass + 0.75 phr pMDI under flexural static loading showing good matrix-fibre interface adhesion.

Observations of Figs. 13, 15, 16 and 18 do not permit to find any significant effect of fatigue loading on the failure modes pattern of the fracture surfaces for these two studied materials, except the adhesion quality at the matrix-fibre interface shown in Figs. 15 and 18.

Fig. 13. SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of a specimen of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG composite under fatigue loading at 40% of flexural static strength, R=0.1, 5Hz.

Fig. 14. Details of the three different zones presented in fig. 14: (a) tensile failure, (b) middle, (c) compressive failure.

Fig. 15. SEM micrograph of fracture surface of a specimen of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG composite under fatigue loading at 40% of flexural static strength, R=0.1, 5 Hz showing poor matrix-fibre interface adhesion.

Fig. 16. SEM micrograph of the fracture surfaces of a specimen of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG + 0.75 phr pMDI composite under fatigue loading at 40% of flexural static strength, R=0.1, 5Hz (more details are shown in fig. 18).

Fig. 17. Details of the three different zones presented in fig. 17: (a) tensile failure, (b) middle, (c) compressive failure.

Fig. 18. SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of a specimen of PHBV/PABT+30wt% SG + 0.75 phr pMDI composite under fatigue loading at 40% of flexural static strength, R=0.1, 5Hz showing good matrix- fibre interface adhesion.

Finally, effect of loading modes (static and fatigue) on the fracture surface of specimens of the two studied materials cannot be identified clearly by comparison between Figs. 7, 10, 13 and 16.

4 Conclusion

Results of the mechanical tests suggest that the compatibilizer enhanced the flexural strengths of the composites under static and fatigue loadings. This positive effect on the strengths is supported by the fracture surface morphology investigation which confirms the good fibre-matrix adhesion in the case of biocomposite containing compatilizer. As for failure mechanisms, tensile and compressive modes are observed on the V shape fracture surfaces of tested specimens under both cases of loading. The same pattern is found for the two studied materials.

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References

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